

BUILDING TRUST IN A WORK ENVIRONMENT THROUGH HUMAN RELATIONS AND VALUES

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Abstract

Trust is very essential for realizing the aims, objectives, vision and mission of an organization. Trust in a work environment promote good team spirit, peace, high productivity, all round well-being for individuals and the company. The presence of trust in a work environment leads to efficiency, effectiveness and high return on investments. It also ensure good rapport and camaraderie between workers across different levels. This paper attempts to discuss the importance of trust in a work environment, its concept, construct and model. It also highlights causes of mistrust and strategies for building trust in a workplace. It recommends that managers should promote trust between workers and their clients for organizational wellbeing and growth.

Introduction

One of the key elements of organizational growth that is often talks less about is “Trust”. Trust is critical in bonding in a work environment. It is critical in internal cohesion and smooth administration. Trust is the end value. It does not depend on any other values to be available before it can exist. There can be no effective team building or organizational change without trust. According to LouDubois, “..... trust is the most important element in building a winning team”. Therefore, trust is the heartbeat of organizational growth or change. Trust is the cornerstone that optimizes performance and productivity. According to Templer (2015; p.5), “Everyone wants to be valued and useful.” Human values, usefulness and good relationships are outcomes of trust. To succeed as a manager, it is imperative to develop a strong relationship with the employees and clients based on trust. “When employees trust and respect their managers, they will give special efforts especially when they feel trusted and supported.” (Source: **Exceptional Results-LMN BLOG**: 10 ways to Build Trust in your Organisation; 2014). When there is a trust in a workplace, almost everything else is easier and comfortable to achieve.

Concept of Trust

“Trust is a state of readiness for unguarded interaction with someone or something.” (Duance, C. 1993). “Trust is telling the truth, even when it is difficult, and being truthful, authentic and trustworthy in your dealings with customers and staff.” (Susan M. Heathfield, 2013). According to Tway, (1993), trust is the necessary precursor for:

- a. feeling able to rely upon a person;
- b. co-operating with and experiencing team work with a group;
- c. taking thoughtful risks; and
- d. experiencing believable communication.

Components of Trust

There are two main components of trust: Character and Competence.

- i. **Character:** This consists of intents and integrity.
 - Intents: This involves caring, transparency and openness.
 - Integrity: This includes honesty, fairness and authenticity.
- ii. **Competence:** This also has two parts; “capability” and “results”
 - Capability: This in terms of skills, knowledge and experience.
 - Results: This also entails Reputation, credibility and performance.

Construct of Trust

Tway (1993) calls trust a construct because it is constructed by three components viz:

- i. **Capacity for Trusting:** Your total life experiences have developed your current capacity and willingness to risk trusting others.
- ii. **Perception of Competence:** This is made up of your ability and the ability of others with whom you work to perform competently whatever is needed in your current situation.

- iii. **Perception of Intentions:** This is defined by Tway as your perception that the actions, words, direction, mission and decisions are motivated by mutually-serving rather than self-serving motives.

Contiguous Trust Model

In a given work environment, there are four different stakeholders whose trusts are highly imperative for growth and necessary change. These consist of the executives, managers, employees and clients (outsiders). Both the executives, individual managers and employees operate mainly within the system. They interact regularly, while the clients have occasional contacts with the executives and the managers. However, there are constant contacts between the ordinary employees and the clients. For the organization to function effectively there must be a synergy of trust between the four critical stakeholders. They must have mutual trust on one another to ensure organizational growth and change. This is called contiguous trust. There must be continuous touch between them. Each must believe in one another. The absence of trust by any of the stakeholders will be inimical to the growth and good health of the organization. In this model, because of the trust between the individuals, each develop confidence and love for the organization. Each person now sees himself/herself as a stakeholder and is ready to give his or her best. The results are good policies emanating from the executives, managers' good implementation of executive policies. The employees are motivated for higher productivity and the clients derive satisfaction and are willing to do more business with the organization. At the end, the desired organizational growth, good returns and changes are experienced. **Figure 1** below shows the expected qualities and relationships between the four stakeholders. It shows that trust leads to positive organizational climate, higher productivity, client satisfaction and increased demand.

Fig 1: Contiguous Trust Model

Causes of Mistrust in a Work Environment

Mistrust in organizational setting could arise as a result of:

- i. Misunderstood communication: if there is no clarity in information, it could lead to mistrust. Ambiguity in relaying information causes mistrust. It is counterproductive for managers to hide information (no matter how little) from their superiors, co-workers and clients. Equally, if messages are not properly relayed, it breeds mistrust. Organization becomes toxic if employees or clients are misinformed, misdirected or misled.
- ii. When there is partiality, discrimination or favouritism: Mistrust thrives in an environment if leaders deliberately refused to raise questions or act when there are obvious mistakes by selected individuals. Using double standards breeds mistrust.

The practice of chosen one syndrome is a twin to mistrust. If managers begin to segregate employees as super-stars and non-stars, there will be grave mistrust. Equally, when clients are not treated with equity; there will be lack of confidence.

- iii. Perceived lack of competence of the leadership by the employees. Leadership competence breeds confidence and trust. Subordinates trust sense of judgment of managers who are skilful and knowledgeable. There is reliance by subordinates on competent leaders for direction and guidance on difficult tasks. Incompetent leadership is directly responsible for lack of trust by both lesser staff and clients.
- iv. Life experiences: This is unwillingness of people to trust due to previous life experiences. Life experiences have impact in shaping trust in oneself and behaviours at work. Uncertainties and problems are easily navigated through trust in oneself, others and system. Mistrust due life experiences negatively have impact on job performance and organizational growth.
- v. Lack of integrity by managers. If a leader lacks integrity, the subordinates and clients will mistrust the manager and the system.
- vi. Lack of patience and empathy by the managers. Leaders are expected to have patience and empathy. Outbursts and insensitivity are banes of trust in any work environment. Intolerance and impatience create to drawback and mistrust.

Succinctly put, one of the effects of mistrust in an organization is that employees do not trust who they perceived does not trust them. This breeds decline productivity as team members play politics and spend quality time to cover up themselves and compliant to the dictates that are counter-productive. (Source: **Exceptional Results – The LMA Blog, 2014: “10 ways to build trust in your organisation”**). Mistrust impart negatively on morale and customer’s satisfaction as

employees shift energy and focus from working on real issues that affects customers or clients to resentment and dissatisfaction towards Management.

Strategies for Building Trust in a Workplace

Building trust in a work environment involves:

- (i) Establish and Maintain Honesty and Integrity.
 - ❖ Honesty and integrity are the foundation of trust in any organization. This must begin from the top (leadership by example). Leaders must be transparent, honest and have high level of integrity to build trust at work.
 - ❖ Managers must be consistently truthful regardless of circumstances. When managers demonstrate openness about their actions, intentions and visions, employees will respond positively.
 - ❖ Managers should share good and bad news openly to eliminate gossip and diffuse inappropriate politics. Relevant information in office must be readily available to all stakeholders. This builds confidence of workers and act as impetus for individuals to contribute more to organizational growth. Individuals with adequate information of their workplace have a sense of belonging, they usually go extra miles to defend policies and direction of such organization.
 - ❖ Managers must be ready to admit mistakes rather than ignore them or cover up. Cover up is the greatest enemy of trust. Leaders must be humble enough to apologize for errors committed. They should not create a negative impression that they know it all. Staff and clients should be made to know that to err is human.

- ❖ Managers must demonstrate a moral soundness of strong values, methods and principles. They should always keep their words. Avoid broken promises. Keeping commitments will foster trust. Leaders must be principled in their conducts and relationship with significant persons in a work environment.
- (ii) Establish Strong Business Ethics: Managers must confront hard issues in a timely fashion. There should be no vacillation. Trust is built and deep-rooted when matters are treated with utmost dispatch and transparency. Files and correspondences must be attended to as they come. Delay in treating matters always create mistrust.
- (iii) Communicate Vision and Values: The vision and mission of an organization should very plain and unambiguous. Managers should be able to communicate easily the aims and objectives the organization stands for. The stakeholders should know what managers are talking about (clarity) at a given time. Admit it, if you don't know. Do not pretend to know and give faulty information. Employees forgive a lack of knowledge but will never forgive a liar or pretender.
- (iv) Role clarity: Roles must be cleared and well-defined. Avoid ambiguities in assigning responsibilities. Lack of roles breed conflicts, unhealthy rivalries, chaos and total breakdown of rules and regulations. Therefore, individual workers should be assigned specific roles by managers. Workers must know their specific line managers or supervisors. Two masters cannot be in a boat. Schedules of duties must be well delineated to avoid problems. When individual workers are assigned specific responsibilities they always excel and are more productive. This is because they see themselves as contributing meaningfully to the system. They can make boast of their membership and have trust in the Management.

- (v) Managers should give their workers latitudes to express themselves. Allow them to use their initiatives. Give them a job to do and let them get on with it. Occasionally crosscheck what they are doing to ensure they are doing the right thing. This makes them to build up confidence and trust.
- (vi) To get trust leaders need to give trust. Whatever a leader sow is what he/she reaps. Employees act with integrity and keep commitments when leadership trust them. Managers must not deceive to attain desired short term goals. It will definitely backfire in the nearest future. The golden rule is: **Trust breeds Trust.**
- (vii) Managers must keep interactions consistent, open and predictable from the beginning. Leaders should be accessible and responsive. They should be regularly available to team members. Leaders must be responsive in interacting with both workers and customers. Do not ignore or look down of people. See and make everyone important by applauding their contributions no matter how little they may be.
- (viii) Leaders must maintain confidences. Do not be flippant about organizational and individual secrets. People trust those who they can share their secrets (personal and official) with. Trust thrives in an atmosphere where secrets are kept sacrosanct. Managers must therefore be careful with the type of information they reel out in order not endanger trust people have in them and the organization.
- (ix) As a leader, be patient and have empathy. Listen to others with respect and full attention. Do not be in a haste to jump into conclusion on matters brought before you. Have a listening ear and be ready to solve issues that confront your subordinates. Empathize with people. Put yourself in their positions. Feel for them and make them realize that you can be relied upon. Share your experience with them on similar

- situation and let them know how deal with such circumstances. This buoys their confidences and trust.
- (x) Leaders should create social time for the team. All work without play makes Jack a dull guy. Leaders must be not aloof, dull and uninteresting. They should create funs, have time outs, gist occasionally and maintain a social platform where people can relate well. Management should organize annual get-together and award nights where people are appreciated. These bring about congeniality and camaraderie in the system.
 - (xi) One of the hallmark of building trust at workplace is impartiality. Managers must be seeing as protecting the interests of all the employees in a work group. Nepotism must be discouraged. Do not talk about other employees, nor allow others to place blame, call names, or point fingers. Subordinates learn to trust when they know their names are not being taken in vain. Fair treatment must demonstrated at all time.
 - (xii) Finally, managers should appreciate the little contributions of others. Human beings thrive and have trust in a system that appreciate their efforts. Therefore, managers should avoid blatant condemnation. They should correct or reproof with decorum. Build up the psyche of others by making them feel important and part of the system. Buying little gift items to appreciate subordinates for their contributions goes a long way in engendering trust. In addition, giving occasional pep talks are catalysts to trust in leadership. Helping workers to realize their potentials despite their inadequacies leads to great trust and higher productivity.

CONCLUSION

According to Hickman (2005), people in organizations embrace or eschew complete trust based on a combination of experience, personality and motivations. For this reason, it is very difficult to maintain high levels of trust in an organization without a strong culture that promotes nature and

even demand it. Every leader should therefore discourage doubt, suspicions, mistrust, disbelieve, cynicism and paranoia. “An atmosphere of trust, belief, hope, faith and confidence should be allowed to prevail to bring about desired organizational growth and change.” (Hickman, 2005). In summary, Templer (2015; p. 25) advised managers to: “Build your team and then trust them to get on with it.” Abiding with this advice will go a long way in building trust at work.

REFERENCES

- Barett Values Centre (2014). The New leadership Paradigm. *tnlp.valuescenter.com*
- Craig. R. Hickman (2005). Management Malpractice. Massachusetts: Platinum Press, Massachusetts.
- Duane. C. (1993). A Construct of Trust, Dissertation. Quoted by Susan M. Heathfield in an Article titled: 10 Most Important Secret about Trust.
- Lou Dubois (2014). How to Build a Corporate Culture of Trust: *www.inc.com/guide*
- Susan M. Heathfield (2013). Top 10 ways to Build Trust at Work: An article contribution at *About.com Human Resources*.
- Susan M. Heathfield (2014) Trust Rules: The Most Important Secret about Trust. *About. Com.Human Resources*.
- Templer R. (2015). The Rules of Management. Edinburgh Pearson Education Ltd.
- The LMA Blog (2013). 10 Ways to Build Trust in your Organization Exceptional Results. *The LMABlog*.